

Analysis of N-LIST Non-Users of the Select Degree Colleges Affiliated to Panjab University, Chandigarh

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This research paper analyze the N-LIST non-users among the student and faculty members of the various select Degree Colleges affiliated to Panjab University, Chandigarh. A questionnaire method was used as a tool for collection of data from the 32 select degree colleges in Punjab and Chandigarh. The five questionnaires were designed to collect the data from the respondents and to identify the non-users. The total data was collected from the 466 out of 513 respondents. The total response rate is 90.84%. Out of 466 respondents, total 286 are users (faculty and student) respondents and 180 are non-users (faculty and student) respondents. The statistical test have been applied and the inferences have been drawn thereof.

Keywords: E-Books, E-Journals, Bibliographical Databases, N-LIST, INFLIBNET, Usage of E-Resources, Degree Colleges of Panjab University, Statistical Analysis, Consortia, Non-Users

0 INTRODUCTION

With the advent of resource sharing, the Library Consortia have brought economy, efficiency and equality in information availability and its usage.

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Through Library Consortia, the gap between information resource-rich libraries and resource-deficient libraries is expected to be bridged. Although, there are many consortia in India like UGC-INFONET Digital Library Consortia, INDEST Consortia, CSIR Consortia etc which have already gained the popularity in India. Yet, N-LIST is one of such consortia which helps to bridge this gap and provides access to the E-resources to its users.

1 N-LIST: AN INITIATIVE OF NMEICT

The National Mission on Education through Information and Communication Technology (NMEICT) was launched on 3rd Feb, 2009. It initiated a project called “National Library and Information Services Infrastructure for Scholarly Content (N-LIST)”, popularly known as N-LIST which was formally launched by Shri Kapil Sibal, Union Minister for Human Resource Development, on 4th May, 2010. (ref. 1) The N-LIST Project is being jointly executed by the (University Grants Commission- Information Network) UGC-INFONET Digital Library Consortium, INFLIBNET Centre and the INDEST-AICTE Consortium, Indian Institute of Technology (IIT) Delhi. The project provides the cross-subscription to e-resources subscribed by the two Consortia, i.e. subscription to INDEST-AICTE resources for universities and UGC-INFONET resources for technical institutions; and the access to selected e-resources to colleges.

The Faculty and the students from the colleges covered under section 12B/2F of UGC Act are eligible to access e-resources through the N-LIST project. These colleges are required to register themselves on the N-LIST Website. During the last three years, the collection has increased from 2,100 to 6,000 e-journals and from 51,000 to 1,00,000 e-books subscribed under the N-LIST Project.

2 REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Akinola¹ obtained the results from her study which revealed that majority of the respondents (35.4%) from the University of Ibadan sought information to update knowledge. It was also found that the respondents also sought information for writing of papers or books, reading, and for preparing class lectures. The similar study by **Bhardwaj & Walia**² analyse the rating of the quality of the Electronic Resources in the St. Stephens College library, where majority of the respondents (52.8%) agreed that the ‘**Quality of the N-LIST e-resources are excellent**’ while 39.68% of the respondents rated the quality of the N-LIST e-resources were good. The authors also concluded that most of the respondents rated N-LIST e-resources very good. The study on Information seeking behaviour of Social Science Faculty was done by **Chattwal**³ which

indicates the pen-drive is most preferred as an external storage device due to its large storage capacity as well as convenience of usage was found to be the most preferred by 50.20% participants database appears to be the most suitable usage pattern for the University faculty members. Present study indicates that the main reasons for not using N-LIST E-resources are due to 'lack of awareness' by student non-users respondents. A similar study by **Nikam & Pramodini (2007)**⁶ indicates that reasons of non-use of UGC-INFONET resources by the Faculty Members and research scholars was 59.50% of respondents attributed the reason as lack of training/ orientation. The other reason included 28.50% of respondents attributed the reasons as 'lack of awareness' whereas 10.50% opted 'Aware but internet connection is not proper'. The authors concluded that the use was marginal and the scientist in the Mysore University Campus need constant guidance and training to maximise the use of UGC-INFONET e-resources. The similar study by **Chikkanmanju and Kumbhar(2015)**⁴ identified the level of satisfaction of student respondents about the information retrieved through the N-LIST E-resources of the Tumkur University. The study reveals that 46.86% opined that the aided college students are extremely satisfied with the information retrieved through the N-LIST E-resources.

3 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The present study is an attempt to find out the accessibility of N-LIST E-resources and the usage trends used by the faculty and students of the Panjab University, Chandigarh.

The study was conducted with the following objectives:-

- i. To identify the N-LIST non-users from the various Degree Colleges of Panjab University, Chandigarh
- ii. To analyse the reasons for not using the N-LIST E-resources among the Non-Users.

4 HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

H₀ 1- There is no significant association in the awareness programmes and the non-users (faculty and students).

H₁ - There is significant association in the awareness programmes and the non-users (faculty and students).

5 METHODOLOGY AND SCOPE OF THE STUDY

A Survey method has been implemented to meet the objectives of the study. The author has collected the data through questionnaire method from the select Degree Colleges which are affiliated to Panjab University. In order to seek valuable information from the students, faculty and librarians; five sets of questionnaires have been devised for optimum data collection, first set would be addressed to faculty users and second to the students users. The third and fourth questionnaire would be addressed to the student non-users and faculty non-users, respectively. The fifth set is for the librarians. The data have been collected from the 144 faculty users and 142 student users. In 144 faculty users, 114 are males and 30 are females whereas 142 student users, 33 are males and 109 are females. The statistical Chi-test has been applied to approve the null or alternate hypothesis. This method facilitates yearly accumulation of information from the member colleges in various settings under parameters relevant to the study.

6 RESPONSE RATE

Table 1: User Population

Stratum	Population Size N (%)	Sample Size N (%)	Users Response N (%)	Non - users Response N (%)	Total Response N (%)
Faculty	1664 (48.64%)	250 (48.73%)	144 (64.86%)	78 (35.14%)	222 (88.80%)
Student	1757 (51.36%)	263 (51.27%)	142 (58.20%)	102 (41.80%)	244 (92.78%)
Total (N %)	3421 (100.00%)	513 (100.00%)	286 (61.37%)	180 (38.63%)	466 (90.84%)

In the present study, the total population size is 3421 in which 48.64% (1664) are faculty members and 51.35 % (1757) are student. According to **Krejcie and Morgan**, after applying the **Proportionate Random Stratified Sampling** have been implied, the sample size of faculty members and student came out to be 250 i.e. 48.73% and 263 i.e. 51.27%, respectively.

Users Verses Non-users Response Rate

Figure: 1

The response rate is 90.84%. Out of 466, 61.37% are user respondents and 38.63% are non-users respondents. The above figure demonstrates that the response rates of the users are higher than that of the non-users.

Faculty Responses

■ Faculty Users Response
 ■ Faculty Non - users Response

Figure: 2

Students Responses

■ Student Users Response
 ■ Student Non - users Respor

Figure: 3

The above figure demonstrates the faculty responses which are divided into faculty user respondent's i.e. 64.86% (144) and faculty non-user respondents are 35.14% (78). Similarly, the response rate of student' users and non-user respondents are 58% (142) and 41.80% (102), The total Faculty and Student Response Rate is 88.80% and 92%, respectively. It has been revealed that the student' response rate is overall high as compared to faculty response rate. It has been examined that Faculty Users' response rate is high as compared to the student response rate. Further the table shows that the student' non-users responses are more as compared to faculty non-users responses

61 DEMOGRAPHY FACULTY & STUDENT (NON-USER)

Demography refers to the fundamental and measurable statistics of a population with characteristics such as gender, age, education of the faculty and student users. The below table provides demographic statistics of student Users' respondents in terms of gender, age and education. The analysis of the data has been done in the following manner:-

Table 2: DEMOGRAPHY FACULTY & STUDENT (NON-USERS)

Demography		Student	Demography		Faculty
		N (%)			N (%)
Gender	Male	57 55.88%	Gender	Male	25 32.05%
	Female	45 44.12%		Female	53 67.95%
Age	18-21	11 10.78%	Age	25-34	22 28.21%
	22-24	76 74.51%		35-44	29 37.18%
	More than 24 years	15 14.71%		Above 44	27 34.62%
Education	Graduate	77 75.49%	Designation	Professor	39 50.00%
	Post Graduate	25 24.51%		Associate Professor	16 20.51%
				Assistant Professor	23 29.49%

62 GENDER

Figure: 4

The above figure illustrates the Gender wise distribution of respondents is presented. The responses have been received from male and female non-users respondents from the colleges under investigation. It has been analysed that out of 78 faculty non-users, 67.95% respondents are females while 32.05% are the males whereas among the student non-users, out of total 102 respondents, 44.12% are females and 55.88% are males. The above data reveals that the

representation of female respondents is higher in the faculty non users than in the student non-users' respondents.

63 AGE

Figure: 5

The above figure shows that in the faculty age group, the respondents 28.21%, 37.18% and 34.62% lies in the age -groups of “25-34”, “35-44” and “more than 44”, respectively. While in case of student age group, the respondents 10.78%, 74.51% and 14.71% fall in the age-groups i.e. “18-21”, “22-24” and “more than 24 years”, respectively. From the above data, it is clear that in the Faculty non- users, the majority of respondents i.e. 37.18% lies in the age-group of 35-44 years whereas in the Student non- users, the highest respondents i.e. 74.51% falls in the age-group of 22-24 years. It is also revealed that the majority of the respondents from both student and faculty non- users fall within the middle age-groups categories.

64 DESIGNATION

Figure: 6

From the above figure, it has been perceived that the designations of the faculty non-users include Assistant Professors, Associate Professors and Professors. A majority of the respondents are from the categories of Professor Designation i.e.50.00% followed by 29.49% respondents in the Category of Assistant Professor and least respondents i.e. 20.51% in the Category of Associate Professor. It shows that the overall faculty non Users' respondent lies in the highest designation.

65 STUDENT EDUCATION

In case of Student Non-Users Education group, the above table displays that 75.49% of respondents are pursuing graduation, while 24.51% are pursuing Post-graduation. It has been surveyed that the overall non-users respondents are pursuing the graduation degree and they are least interested in using the N-LIST E-resources.

66 DISCIPLINE

The questionnaires also attempted to ascertain the disciplines/ core-subjects to which the Non-users respondents belonged to. The disciplines are divided into three groups Arts, Science and Commerce. The Education Colleges (its faculty and student) have also been included in the Arts Discipline. This helped us in determining the various information requirements of the faculty and student in relation to the disciplines they belonged to Table 3.

Table: 3: DISCIPLINE

Sr. No.	Disciplines	Arts N (%)	Science N (%)	Commerce N (%)	Total
1.	Faculty Non-Users	31 39.74%	17 21.79%	30 38.46%	78 100%
2.	Student Non-Users	30 29.41%	46 45.10%	26 25.49%	102 100%
Total		61 33.89%	63 35.00%	56 31.11%	180 100%

Faculty Non-Users

STUDENT NON-USERS

Figure: 7

It was found that in the faculty non-users, the highest number of respondents i.e. 39.74% are from Arts discipline followed by 38.46% of respondents from the Commerce and 21.79% respondents belong to Science disciplines.

Whereas in the student non-users category, 45.10% of participants are from the Science discipline followed by 29.41% who belong to Arts discipline and 25.49% of Commerce discipline, respectively. The above table also reveals that the highest students non-user's respondents are from the Science discipline while in faculty non-users respondents are from the Arts discipline.

7 (A) REASONS FOR NOT USING N-LIST E-RESOURCES BY FACULTY NON-USERS

Table: 4: (Faculty) Reasons for not using N-LIST E-resources

Sr. No.	Factors/ Reasons	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
		N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	
1.	Not aware	28 35.90%	31 39.74%	0 0.00%	19 24.36%	0 0.00%	78 100.00%
2.	Aware but lack of quality time	0 0.00%	60 76.92%	0 0.00%	18 23.08%	0 0.00%	78 100.00%
3.	Aware but poor internet connection	0 0.00%	63 80.77%	0 0.00%	15 19.23%	0 0.00%	78 100.00%
4.	Aware but lack of training	0 0.00%	68 87.18%	10 12.82%	0 0.00%	0 0.00%	78 100.00%
5.	Aware but lack of library support	0 0.00%	67 85.90%	4 5.13%	7 8.97%	0 0.00%	78 100.00%
6.	Aware but lack of Wi-Fi facility	0 0.00%	72 92.31%	0 0.00%	6 7.69%	0 0.00%	78 100.00%
7.	of low value/ Inadequate Information	0 0.00%	64 82.05%	7 8.97%	7 8.97%	0 0.00%	78 100.00%
8.	Prefer searching Web Search Engine	5 6.41%	59 75.64%	0 0.00%	14 17.95%	0 0.00%	78 100.00%
9.	Limited Subject coverage	12 15.38%	56 71.79%	0 0.00%	10 12.82%	0 0.00%	78 100.00%
10.	Printed books /journals are adequate to me	0 0.00%	63 80.77%	0 0.00%	15 19.23%	0 0.00%	78 100.00%

From combining the scores of 'Strongly Agree' (SA) and 'Agree' (A), it has been assessed that the majority of faculty respondents i.e. 92.31% (SA= 0.00% + A= 92.31%) considered that they are **'aware but lack of Wi-Fi'**

facility followed by 87.18% (SA= 0.00% + A= 87.18%) who are ‘aware but lack of training’ are one of the major reason for not using the N-LIST E-resources. While 87.17% (SA= 15.38% + A= 71.79%) of faculty respondents feels that N-LIST E-resources have limited subject coverage. Whereas 82.05% (SA= 6.41% + A= 75.64%) of faculty respondents prefer searching WSE than the N-LIST E-resources. While 80.77% faculty non-user’s respondents who prefer searching through printed books and journals. Whereas 82.05% of faculty respondents feel that the information retrieved is of low value/ inadequate information from the N-LIST E-resources as a reasons/ factors for not using N-LIST E-resources. While 76.92% of faculty respondents are ‘**aware but lack of quality time**’ access is considered one of the reason for not using the N-LIST E-resources.

From the scores of ‘Strongly Disagree’, it is obvious that no respondent have opted for this option. It have been evinced that the faculty non-users have one or another reasons or factors for not using the N-LIST E-resources. The administration and the INFLIBNET authorities must take the reasons of the non-users into considerations for effective usage of the N-LIST E-resources.

From the scores of ‘Disagree’, it has been apparent that the 24.36% of the faculty respondents didn’t agree that they lack of awareness is not the reason for not using the N-LIST E-resources whereas 23.19% also disagrees that they are aware but lack of access is not the reason for not using the N-LIST E-resources.

It can be inferred that majority of the faculty non-users i.e. 92.31% who considered **lack of Wi-Fi facility** as one of the major factors/ reasons for not using N-LIST E-resources.

71 REASONS FOR NOT USING N-LIST E-RESOURCES BY STUDENT NON-USERS

Table 5: (Student) Reasons for not using N-LIST E-resources

Sr. No.	Factors/ Reasons	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
		N (%)					
1.	Not aware	73 71.57 %	7 6.86 %	22 21.57 %	0 0.00 %	0 0.00%	102 100.00 %
2.	Aware but lack of quality time	0 0.00 %	65 63.73 %	37 36.27 %	0 0.00 %	0 0.00%	102 100.00 %
3.	Aware but poor internet connection	49 48.04 %	18 17.65 %	19 18.63 %	16 15.6 9%	0 0.00%	102 100.00 %
4.	Aware but lack of training	19 18.63 %	36 35.29 %	34 33.33 %	13 12.7 5%	0 0.00%	102 100.00 %
5.	Aware but lack of library support	2 1.96 %	42 41.18 %	47 46.08 %	11 10.7 8%	0 0.00%	102 100.00 %
6.	Aware but lack of wi-fi facility to use	16 15.69 %	20 19.61 %	66 64.71 %	0 0.00 %	0 0.00%	102 100.00 %
7.	Of low value/ Inadequate Information	0 0.00 %	0 0.00 %	68 66.67 %	34 33.3 3%	0 0.00%	102 100.00 %
8.	Prefer searching Web Search Engine	0 0.00 %	0 0.00 %	58 56.86 %	44 43.1 4%	0 0.00%	102 100.00 %
9.	Limited subject coverage	0 0.00 %	42 41.18 %	60 58.82 %	0 0.00 %	0 0.00%	102 100.00 %
10.	printed books/journals are adequate for me	60 58.82 %	18 17.65 %	11 10.78 %	13 12.7 5%	0 0.00%	102 100.00 %
11.	Language Barrier (doesn't able to understand the language)	47 46.07 %	26 25.49 %	11 10.78 %	16 15.6 9%	2 1.96%	102 100.00 %
12.	Lack of personal devices (Personal Computers/ Laptops / Smart phones/ tablets etc)	0 0.00 %	50 49.01 %	50 49.02 %	0 0.00 %	2 1.96%	102 100.00 %

From combining the scores of 'Strongly Agree' (SA) and 'Agree' (A), it has been interpreted that the majority of student respondents i.e. 78.43% (SA= 71.57% + A= 6.87%) considered 'lack of awareness' regarding N-LIST E-resources as the major reason for not using the N-LIST E-resources followed by 76.47% (SA= 58.82% + A= 17.65%) who think that 'printed books/ journals are adequate for them'. While 71.56% (SA= 46.07% + A= 25.49%) considered 'language barrier' and 65.69% (SA= 48.04% + A= 17.65%) considered that they are 'aware but poor internet connection' are one of the hindrances for not using the N-LIST E-resources.

From the scores of 'Strongly Disagree', it is clearly only 1.96% of student respondent does not think that 'language barrier' and 'Lack of personal devices' is one of the reason for not using it.

From the scores of 'Disagree', it can be perceived that the 43.14% of the student respondents disagree that they prefer searching through google and 33.33% also disagree that the N-LIST E-resources are of low value. While 15.69% of student respondents doesn't have any language barrier.

It can be inferred that majority of student respondents i.e. 78.43% (SA= 71.57% + A= 6.87%) considered '**lack of awareness**' regarding N-LIST E-resources as the major reason for not using the N-LIST E-resources followed by 76.47% (SA= 58.82% + A= 17.65%) who think that 'printed books/ journals are adequate for them'

Present study indicates that the main reasons for not using N-LIST E-resources are due to 'lack of awareness' by student non-users respondents. A similar study by **Nikam&Pramodini (2007)**⁶ indicates that reasons of non-use of UGC-INFONET resources by the Faculty Members and research scholars was 59.50% of respondents attributed the reason as lack of 'adequate training/ orientation'. The other reason included 28.50% of respondents attributed the reasons as 'lack of awareness' whereas 10.50% opted 'Aware but internet connection is inappropriate'. The authors concluded that the use was marginal and the scientist in the Mysore University Campus required constant guidance and training to maximise the use of UGC-INFONET e-resources.

72 REASONS FOR NOT USING N-LIST E-RESOURCES:FACULTY VS STUDENTS NON-USERS

It can be assessed that majority of the faculty non-users considered lack of Wi-Fi facility whereas the student respondents considered 'lack of awareness' regarding N-LIST E-resources as the major reason for not using the N-LIST E-resources. It can be perceived that in the scores of strongly disagree, the faculty respondents have not opted, which simply evinced that the faculty have one or another reason for not using the N-LIST E-resources. On the contrary, it can be

manifested that only 1.96% of respondents strongly disagrees that ‘language barrier’ and ‘Lack of personal devices’ is one of the reason for not using it.

8 TESTING OF HYPOTHESIS (NON-USERS)

Hypotheses H₀7- There is no significant association in the awareness programmes and the non-users (faculty and students)

H₁7- There is significant association in the awareness programmes and the non-users (faculty and students)

Table 6: Sources of Awareness by Faculty and Students Non-Users

Sr. No.	Source of Awareness	Faculty Non Users N (%)	Student Non Users N (%)
1.	Institute’s Website	28 35.90%	3 2.94%
2.	Institute’s Prospectus	6 7.69%	10 9.80%
3.	Library user Orientation Programme	2 2.56%	4 3.92%
4.	Friends /Colleagues	6 7.69%	5 4.90%
5.	Library Notice Board	3 3.85%	3 2.94%
6.	Library Staff	3 3.85%	2 1.96%
7.	N-List Face Book	2 2.56%	2 1.96%
8.	Not Aware	28 35.90%	73 71.58%
Total		78 100%	102 100%
Chi-Square d.f.	39.7 7	p-value	0.000

Source of Awareness

Figure: 8

The faculty non user respondents were asked that from which of the above mentioned sources the faculty non users are aware of the N-LIST E-resources. A majority of faculty respondents i.e. 35.90% sought awareness from the Institute website followed by 7.69% who feels that they seek awareness from their friends/ colleagues about the N-LIST E-resources. 3.85% of the respondents get aware from the library staff whereas only 7.69% and 2.56% get aware from the Institute prospectus and library orientation programme respectively. There are 2.56% and 3.85% respondents get awareness about N-LIST E-resources from face book Page and from Library notice board. But 35.90% of respondents were not aware of the N-LIST e-resources.

In case of student non- users, a majority of respondents 9.80% sought awareness from the Institute's prospectus followed by friends. Only 3.92% sought awareness from the Library User Orientation Programmes, whereas 2.94% of student non-users respondents sought awareness from library notice boards and Institute's websites. Only 1.96% was aware from library staff and N-LIST Face book page. The 71.58% of the student respondents were not aware of N-LIST E-resources, which are the major reasons for the students' low membership in the N-LIST amongst the various member colleges undertaken in the study. The researcher has observed that the students wish to use the e-resources but they were not aware of it. Although there are faculty member who were not aware but ratio of faculty members is small than that of the students.

The chi-square value is 39.7 and the p-value for the awareness is 0.000 which is significant at 5%. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate is accepted i.e. there is a significant association in the awareness programmes and the non-users (faculty and students)

Hence, the finding rejects the Null Hypothesis Ho7.

9 FINDINGS FROM THE NON-USERS PERSPECTIVE

1 Demography

- i.** The representation of female respondents was more in the faculty non users than of the male respondents in student non-user respondents.
- ii.** Among the Faculty non- users, the highest age-group was 35-44 years at 37.2% whereas in the Student non- users, the highest age-group was 22-24 years at 74.5%. It was also revealed that the majority of the respondents from both the students and the faculty non- users lay within the middle age-groups categories.
- iii.** A majority of the faculty non-users respondents were from the categories of Professor Designation i.e.50.0% followed by 29.5% respondents in the Associate Professor and least respondents i.e. 2.1% are in the

designation of Assistant Professor. Thus the overall respondents lay in the highest designation and the least respondents lay in the Assistant Professor designation.

- iv. It was surveyed that the overall non-user respondents were pursuing the graduation degree.

2 Source of Awareness

- i. **71.58%** of the student respondents were '**not aware**' of N-LIST E-resources, which were the major reasons for the students' low membership in the N-LIST amongst the various member colleges undertaken in the study. The researcher has observed that the students wish to use the e-resources but they were not aware of it.
- ii. A majority of faculty respondents i.e. 35.90% sought awareness from the Institute website followed by 7.69% who felt that they seek awareness from their friends/ colleagues about the N-LIST E-resources whereas 35.90% of faculty respondents were not aware of the N-LIST e-resources.

3 Reasons for not using the N-LIST E-resources

- i. It can be inferred that majority of the faculty non-users i.e. 92.31% who considered **lack of Wi-Fi facility** followed by **87.18%** '**aware but lack of training**' as one of the major factors/ reasons for not using N-LIST E-resources.
- ii. 76.92% of faculty respondents were '**aware but lack of quality time**' access was considered one of the reason for not using the N-LIST E-resources.
- iii. Majority of student respondents i.e. 78.43% considered '**lack of awareness**' regarding N-LIST e-resources as the major reason for not using the N-LIST E-resources followed by 76.47% who thinks that '**printed books/ journals were adequate for them**'.
- iv. While 71.56% considered '**language barrier**' and 65.69% considered that they were '**aware but poor internet connection**' were one of the hindrances for not using the N-LIST E-resources.
- v. It can be perceived that the 43.14% of the student respondents **disagree** that they prefer searching **Web Search Engine (WSE)** and 33.33% also **disagrees** that the N-LIST E-resources were of '**low value**'. While 15.69% of student respondents doesn't have any language barrier.

10 SUGGESTIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study at hand was focused on the evaluation of usage of N-LIST E-

resources in the Select Degree Colleges Affiliated to Panjab University, Chandigarh. The libraries should endeavor to launch a marketing plan to promote the usage of N-LIST E-resources and its awareness among the users through email alerts, text messages, social networking sites, whatsapp groups, blogs, and wikis etc. It is suggested that the subscription cost of N-LIST E-resources should be reduced to the same as earlier for the Non-aided colleges also.

Further the research in this regard will widen the criteria of the study and identify as to how the faculty and the student from the member colleges affiliated to other Universities explore the usage of the N-LIST E-resources. The authors feel that there is a need for appropriate and constant evaluation of this study in order to enhance insight into the usage analysis and the relevance of the information retrieved from the N-LIST E-resources.

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